

RADx-UP Community Collaboration

Mini-Grant (C2G)

January 1, 2022 – June 30, 2022

Interim Evaluation Report

September 26, 2022

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Abbreviations

CCPH	Campus Community Partners for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EO	Evaluation Objective
EQ	Evaluation Question
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
SEBI	Social, ethical, and behavioral implications
SECDP	Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination Plan
SEP	Strategic Evaluation Plan
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19 associated morbidity and mortality. The Community Collaboration Mini Grant program (C2G) are awards of up to \$50,000 to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives for underserved populations, as defined by the NIH ¹. Community serving organizations, faith-based organizations, community-based clinics, and tribal nations and organizations are eligible to apply for funding for the C2G program ¹.

This interim evaluation report details the RADx-UP C2G key evaluation findings that indicate RADx-UP C2G program outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts between January 2022 through June 30, 2022. This report is also an opportunity for collaboration with RADx-UP, CDCC, and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

The evaluation of RADx-UP C2G consists of a longitudinal evaluation design utilizing a mixed-methods approach to engage C2G program awardees at three timepoints (6-months, 12-months, and 18-months) and gather data on their project updates, activities, outcomes and use of CDCC support and resources. (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP C2G Evaluation Logic Model](#)). The T&E team is responsible for distributing evaluation surveys, analyzing the data, and communicating results to C2G leadership.

C2G Program Evaluation Overview

The outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impact of the C2G program were measured using application information collected by the CDCC, publicly available publication data, and evaluation surveys. Some of the key findings include:

- As of June 30, 2022, there are a total of **39 C2G projects across four funding cycles**.

- *Outreach challenges* are defined as challenges in establishing channels or engaging in contact with the target population.
- *Testing supply challenges* are defined as difficulty in securing the inputs to testing like supplies or staff.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the T&E team has provided the following recommendations for improving the C2G program. The goal of these recommendations is to support continuous program improvement, program delivery, and quality of administrative support.

- 1. Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC**
 - a. Continue to promote processes that **increase a successful application rate** among project applicants.
 - b. Continue to fund projects that represent geographically diverse, underserved and Covid-19 vulnerable communities.
 - i. Some populations to focus on when recruiting future projects include projects that include **Tribal nation target populations and American Indian/Alaska Native and Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander target populations, as well as residents of nursing homes**. These underserved and COVID-19 vulnerable populations are the least represented among current funded projects.
- 2. Address challenges cited by projects**
 - a. Projects continue to report **challenges related to outreach, testing hesitancy and testing site**
 - b. **Testing supply challenges** were also the most cited roadblock that has been **resolved** by projects. Projects may benefit from learning how others have overcome similar roadblocks.
 - c. Maintaining continuous feedback loops between the UNC Evaluation team, the C2G implementation team and C2G awardees

I. Background

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19 associated morbidity and mortality.

The program seeks to achieve this primary aim through:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved
- Strengthening the available data on disparities in infection rates; disease progression and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address disparities in COVID-19 diagnostics

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supports RADx-UP projects as they serve their communities and serve as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, oversee the CDCC.

This 2022 Interim C2G Evaluation Report specifically covers the evaluation of **the RADx-UP Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Program (C2G)** projects from January 1 through June 30, 2022. The **C2G program** are awards of up to \$50,000 to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives for underserved populations, as defined by the NIH ¹. Community serving organizations, faith-based organizations, community-based clinics, and tribal nations and organizations are eligible to apply for funding for the C2G program ¹.

These results are used by the C2G team to address any issues with awardees in ad hoc meetings and to improve CDCC support and overall understanding of each project's progress towards reaching their intended goals.

Overview of the RADx-UP C2G Evaluation

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assesses the RADx-UP program's productivity and impact by evaluating its projects. The T&E team employs the core components of the Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large. The team also employs the **Most Significant**

Change (MSC) approach³ to better understand program impact, and the values held by different stakeholders. An overview of the RADx-UP C2G aims, outcomes and associated evaluation key measures are found in [Table 1](#).

The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RADx-UP program’s effectiveness, performance, and community engagement.

The purpose of this report is two-fold: 1) describe key evaluation findings that indicate **RADx-UP C2G program** outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts; and 2) collaborate with RADx-UP, CDCC, and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

Table 1. Overview of RADx-UP C2G Aims, Outcomes and Associated Evaluation Key Measures

Overview of Outcomes and Key Measures		
Outcomes	Measures	Survey Tools Used
Aim 1: Improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved populations and COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations		
Increase in individuals reached with testing services or information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of individuals reached through project activities (dependent on project type and activity; will not be available in all cases) • Type of NIH-designated underserved populations and COVID-19 vulnerable populations targeted through projects (per cycle and cumulatively) • Diversity of populations reached (geographically, across underserved and vulnerable population categories) 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys
Aim 2: Support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives		
Collaborations established between C2G awardees and other NIH-supported COVID-19 initiatives Expanded RADx-UP Resource Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of organizations funded (location, organization type) • # of communities of practice established between C2G and RADx-UP awardees • # of collaborations between C2G awardees and CEAL programs • # of new materials/resources added to Resource Library 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys
Aim 3: Increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities.		

Development and dissemination of education materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of training and/or educational events • # of educational materials developed • Types of communications disseminated (PSAs, social media blasts, ads on buses, etc.) • Types of direct community support provided by projects (Transportation services, referrals, etc.) • Strategies to communicate test results/other follow-up measures • # of projects facilitating testing 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys
Community personnel trainings or workshops held		
Transportation or other testing-related support services provided		
Enhanced data collection and surveillance of COVID-19 testing activities		
Effective strategies for communication of COVID-19 test results		
Aim 4: Implement C2G program to maximize impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC		
Recruitment of sufficient number of applicants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of applicants per cycle • # of projects awarded per cycle • # of days between award notification and first invoice • Utilization of RADx-UP resources and support • % of awardees that expended funding in 12-month grant period • Types of CDCC support used • Suggested improvements to CDCC support/resources 	C2G Program Records
Timely launch of projects		6- and 12-month evaluation surveys
Timely completion of projects		
Feedback on utility and quality support		

I. Methods

Data Sources. The evaluation of RADx-UP C2G consists of a longitudinal evaluation design, which involves collecting data from C2G program awardees at three timepoints (6-months, 12-months, and 18-months). Data collection includes gathering data on their project updates, activities, outcomes and use of CDCC support and resources (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP C2G Evaluation Logic Model](#)). See [figure 1](#) for a flow diagram of how the data sources map onto program evaluation.

C2G Program Records

The C2G grant administration leadership team provides grant administration data such as number of applicants per cycle to the T&E team.

Six and 12-month Survey

The 6-month interim and 12-month closeout progress reports surveys (herein referred to as the 6-month and 12-month evaluation surveys) are distributed by the T&E team through REDCap to C2G projects based upon project start dates. Evaluation surveys collect a combination of qualitative and quantitative data to assess progress on project activities, information on collaborations, populations engaged, project roadblocks and CDCC support utility. Items on these evaluation surveys also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the TSBM Framework indicators. Survey questions align with project requirements and expectations as outlined in the RFA.

Follow-up Interview (18 months)

At 18 months from their start dates (six months post-project), C2G projects are asked to participate in interviews conducted remotely by Zoom with the T&E team to assess longer-term impacts of the projects. Topics include any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.). This is also where significant change (SC) stories will be collected³. The current interim report does not contain any eighteen-month interview data- the interviews will begin in the Fall of 2022.

Figure 1 Evaluation Data Sources

Data Analysis. Data is analyzed and shared with C2G leadership via dashboard and evaluation reports. The following products are developed from analysis of data sources.

Six and 12-Month Aggregate Dashboards

Six- and 12-month survey results are descriptively analyzed and summarized by funding award cycle in aggregate dashboards. Data included in these dashboard reports include

- The number and type of projects reporting
- The number and type of partner organizations and type of organization
- Types of communities served
- Project activities
- CDCC support services used
- Satisfaction with CDCC support services
- Ongoing and resolved challenges

These results are used by the C2G implementation team and projects to facilitate any needed updates to the evaluation plan and improvements to the program overall. Open-ended response items are coded as categorical variables and include challenges and roadblocks projects have encountered- both resolved and ongoing.

See [Appendix 3](#) for the most recently developed RADx-UP C2G 6-month Dashboard Report.

Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports

Six and 12-month surveys are analyzed across projects and descriptively summarized cumulatively in biannual T&E Evaluation reports. Open-ended response items are coded as categorical variables. Qualitative data includes questions about ongoing and resolved project challenges and roadblocks. Other qualitative data includes questions that ask about improvements to RADx-UP CDCC support or resources.

Project Impact Profiles. Six-month and 12-month evaluation survey data are also used to create Translational Science Benefits Model project impact profiles ⁴. The C2G implementation team and the T&E teams co-developed each Project's profile with the respective Project. The profiles provide a high-level description of how project outcomes reported on the 12-month evaluation survey align with impact areas of the model as shown in the figure below.

The Translational Sciences Benefit Model is a framework designed to support assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts². The T&E Team plans to use the core components of the TSBM model to evaluate the impact of the C2G Program in demonstrating [the clinical, community, economic and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities](#). The main contribution of the TSBM is its utility in identifying the core areas where testing outreach and strategies developed through the RADx-UP Program provides clinical, public health, economic and policy benefits.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Mode (TSBM) Impact Areas⁴

 CLINICAL	Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)
 COMMUNITY	Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)
 ECONOMIC	Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)
 HEALTH EQUITY	Health Equity Benefits* (accessibility, adaptability, reach)
 POLICY	Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)

*The TSBM Framework has been adapted for this evaluation to include an indicator for Health Equity benefits.

Most Significant Change. The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is an evaluation method that involves collecting significant change stories from the field and having a panel of designated stakeholders select the most significant of these stories³. This informs program impact and unintended changes, how and when a change came to be, and also helps provide an understanding on the values of different stakeholders. The MSC approach will be incorporated into the 18-month follow up interviews where projects will share Significant Change (SC) stories- these are stories where projects share what they feel was the most significant change to result from their project.

II. Results

This evaluation report details the findings from the C2G 6-month and 12-month evaluation survey responses collected between January 1 through June 30, 2022 analyzed and summarized across projects.

A. Process Evaluation Results

C2G Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization

Currently, there are a total of **39 C2G projects across funding cycles** (Cycle 1 n=12 funded projects; Cycle 2=6 funded projects; Cycle 3=5 funded projects, Cycle 4=16 funded projects).

Table 2 below shows how many applications were received and grants awarded in each funding cycle. The number of applicants per cycle has varied, but has been showing an upward trend since cycle two. The application funding rate is affected by available funding and number of applications received. This number has varied but there has been an increase in the overall application score which is tied directly to C2G administration guidance on successful applications. The average number of days between award notification and project initiation is calculated from notice of selection to first invoice paid out. This ties back to the program outcome of timely launch of projects, but it is important to note that project start dates vary significantly based on the project teams sending their information in.

Table 2. Metrics per C2G Funding Cycle for the Grant Application Process

C2G Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Average Number of Days between Award Notification and Project Initiation	Application Funding Rate	% of Awardees that Expended Funding in 12-month grant period
Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 5/28/21	31	12	116 days	38.7%	66.7%
Cycle 2	5/7/21 -8/18/21	11	6	93 days	54.5%	66.7%
Cycle 3	7/2/21 -9/30/21	13	5	138 days	38.5%	--*
Cycle 4	10/29/21 – 2/7/22	32	16	--*	50%	--*

**Data not yet available for this cycle*

In this report, evaluation survey data is presented for:

- Cycle 1 n=12 of 12 total projects
- Cycle 2 n = 6 of 6 total project
- Cycle 3 n = 3 of 5 total project

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. Figure 3 summarizes the results from the 6-month survey regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. In this matrix, satisfaction is defined in terms of...

- Accessibility of the RFA on online platforms
- A well worded and easy to understand RFA that encouraged organizations like theirs to apply
- Easy to follow application process
- Receiving adequate support from RADx-UP CDCC throughout the application process

Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support regarding the application process. **Almost 75 percent of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with each statement** that asked about receiving adequate support to completing their application and having an RFA that was easy to understand and accessible to projects. When asked about the RFA being written in a way that encouraged organizations like theirs to apply, and the steps of the application being easy to follow, most respondents agreed or strongly agreed- but there was one project that **disagreed** with each of those statements.

Figure 3. C2GProject Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support (n= 15 projects reporting)

B. Outcome Evaluation Results

B1. Sociodemographic Results

Characteristics of C2G Projects

Geographic Diversity. C2G funded projects are spread out throughout the US, with the majority located in the Midwest, Northeast, South, and Southwest regions. The figure below shows the geographic diversity of C2G projects across the United States (US).

Organization Type. Figure 5 reflects C2G project’s organization type to provide data on the types of organizations that are funded by the C2G program. Organizations include medical care, faith based, community centers, coalitions, and public health organizations.

Figure 4. C2G Project Geographic Diversity: Total Number of C2G Funded Projects by State as of April 25, 2022 (n= 39) (figure developed by the American Institutes for Research (AIR) for RADx-UP)

Organization Type. Figure 5

reflects C2G project’s organization type to provide data on the types of organizations that are funded by the C2G program. Organizations include medical care, faith based, community centers, coalitions, and public health organizations.

Figure 5. C2G Project Organization Type (n= 21 projects reporting) Cycle 1: n = 12 projects; Cycle 2: n= 6 projects; Cycle 3: n= 3 projects

Underserved Populations Served. See [Figure 6](#) for a breakdown of underserved populations represented by C2G projects. Underserved populations are defined as *populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors*⁵. This data shows that **C2G projects have a wide reach of underserved populations- all populations that fall within underserved populations are being reached.** Of the projects that have reported during this reporting period, Hispanic/Latino, Black/African American, and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations were the most common underserved population served by C2G projects.

Figure 6. Underserved Populations Served by C2G Projects (*n= 21 projects reporting*)
 Cycle 1: *n = 12 projects*; Cycle 2: *n= 6 projects*; Cycle 3: *n= 3 projects*

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served.

See [Figure 7](#) of a breakdown of COVID-19 vulnerable communities represented by C2G projects. COVID-19 vulnerable communities are defined as *populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19*⁶. The figure below shows that when taken together, C2G projects

Figure 7. COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served by C2G Projects (*n= 20 projects reporting*)
 Cycle 1: *n = 11 projects*; Cycle 2: *n= 6 projects*; Cycle 3: *n= 3 projects*

have a wide reach of COVID-19 vulnerable communities- **all communities that fall within the**

COVID-19 vulnerable communities are being reached. Of the projects that have reported during this reporting period, children and adolescents, individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19, and migrant and immigrant communities were the most common COVID-19 vulnerable community served by C2G projects.

Characteristics of C2G Projects' Partners. Figure 8 refers to the projects' community partner organizations. Data is collected during both the 6-month interim survey and 12-month final survey. Projects are asked to indicate if they are collaborating with any organizations, and to list their names. The T&E team then codes this data into themes that represent types of project partners. Most project partners are classified as a community center/case management organization, a faith-based organization, or a medical care organization. Cycle one and cycle two projects have a diverse range of project partners. Only three projects from cycle three are captured in this data, and therefore there may be additional project partners not yet captured.

Figure 8. Characteristics of C2G Projects' Partners (n= 18 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: n = 11 projects; Cycle 2: n= 6 projects; Cycle 3: n= 3 projects

Project Challenges. The T&E team also asked projects to report on any roadblocks or challenges faced so far in completing their project. This includes challenges to sample collection, challenges to testing, test result reporting, and engaging with community members. The T&E team then reviewed these challenges and coded the responses into several categories. See Table 3 for a list of the codes and examples of corresponding quotes.

Of the eight projects that reported on ongoing challenges experienced, the most common were related to outreach and testing supplies. Outreach challenges are defined as challenges in establishing channels or engaging in contact with the target population. Testing supply challenges are defined as difficulty in securing the inputs to testing like supplies or staff.

As challenges are observed, the T&E team is communicating these challenges to leadership so that they can be addressed in a timely manner. Outreach, testing hesitancy and testing site challenges may be opportunities for C2G team to strategize with projects on how to address those challenges.

In addition to asking about ongoing challenges, the evaluation surveys also ask about challenges and roadblocks that have been resolved. **Testing supply challenges were also the most commonly cited roadblock that has been resolved by projects.**

Table 3. Ongoing Challenges Experienced by Projects (n= 8 projects reporting)

Code	Quotes
Outreach	"Our ongoing challenge is in countering COVID-19 fatigue", and "The concern is the limited number of people who have attended the clinics since vaccinations are administered in so many other locations. All of our clinics were held during the early day. We are hoping that with changing the vaccination clinic times, this will change"
Testing Supplies	"Lack of access to testing despite demand"
Structural Barriers	<i>"Due to lack of health insurance, there is uncertainty due to the cost of the test, and whether they will receive a bill later on." "The communities we serve are already experiencing multiple difficulties, including poverty, food insecurity, and poor health. COVID-19 is just another health challenge."</i>
Testing Hesitancy	<i>"Hesitancy from community members getting tested due to fears around sharing their information with authorities and costs."</i>
Testing Site	<i>"Finding sites that will partner with [us] to provide testing."</i>
Climate/Weather	<i>"Post-hurricane displacement continues at a smaller scale."</i>
Social Distancing	<i>"January saw a surge in the Omicron variant of COVID which led to delaying or cancelling in-person events."</i>

B2. C2G Project Outcomes and Impacts

C2G Testing and Enrollment, Project Activities, and Products Developed

In this section, we summarize the results from the 6-month and 12-month Evaluation Surveys regarding the C2G Projects' outcomes and impacts of their research and project activities.

One of C2G program aims is to increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities. Of the 12 projects that reported on this question, **100% of them are engaging their community in testing.** Additionally, **an estimated number of over 27,000 people have been reached through project testing efforts.**

Figure 9. C2G Project Activities (*n*= 21 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: *n* = 12 projects; Cycle 2: *n* = 6 projects; Cycle 3: *n* = 3 projects

Figure 9 illustrates the wide range of activities that C2G projects are engaging in, and the progress that has been made toward meeting this program aim. **Nineteen out of twenty-one projects (90.5%) include an activity to provide training or education to their community around COVID-19 testing projects.** Some examples of training include outreach to community health workers, faith leaders, community members, and community leaders via educational sessions, town halls, focus groups on COVID-19 prevention and how to use at-home test kits. Sixteen out of twenty-one projects (76.2%) are developing and disseminating COVID-19 testing communication materials. Examples include bilingual flyers and handouts distributed around the community, at outreach events, posted on social media, and shared at testing events.

Fewer cycles, if any, are focusing on developing communities of practice with other RADxUP awardees, collaborating with CEAL programs on activities, or providing funding for community personnel training on COVID-19 research.

As part of your project, did you develop any products (toolkits, translation, or educational materials) that have not already been submitted that can be added to the RADx-UP Resource Library?

Figure 10. C2G Products Developed (*n*= 13 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: *n* = 7 projects; Cycle 2: *n* = 5 projects; Cycle 3: *n* = 1 project

Projects were also asked to report if they had developed any products (toolkits, translation, or educational materials), with results reported in **Figure 10**. Of the 13 projects that reported on this question, only two stated that they had developed any products. There are some limitations to how this question was asked; the T&E team is modifying the item wording to improve future data collection and reduce missing data.

C2G Projects' Outcomes Aligned with the Translational Sciences Benefit Model (TSBM) Indicators

In this section, we summarize C2G project outcomes and how they align with the areas of the TSBM framework. Projects are asked to list out their project outcomes in the 12-month evaluation survey, and the T&E team codes this data to determine what areas of the TSBM framework they correspond with. This data is then used to develop Project Impact Profiles. Examples of these Impact Profiles can be found in [Appendix 2](#).

Figure 11 illustrates project outcomes aligned with the TSBM indicators-**Clinical, Community and Public Health, Economic, and Policy**. Most outcomes align with community and public health benefits, since these are mainly community-based interventions focused on a specific community target population. Examples include:

Community and public health benefits:

- Implementation of community-based interventions such as community testing events or mobile testing units.
- Development of COVID-19 educational communications resources such as flyers or social media posts.

Clinical benefits:

- COVID-19 testing procedures, for example, any project that provides COVID tests and results to individuals.

Economic benefits:

- Providing free COVID-19 at home test kits to individuals
- Potential cost savings on transportation costs by utilizing a mobile testing clinic.

Figure 11. C2G Project Outcomes Aligned with the Translational Sciences Benefit Model (TSBM) Indicators (n= 13 projects reporting)

Cycle 1: n = 7 projects; Cycle 2: n = 5 projects; Cycle 3: n = 1 project

III. Recommendations and Conclusion

Recommendations. This section details process and outcome-related recommendations for improving the C2G program based on conclusions from the 6- and 12-month evaluation surveys. The goal of these recommendations is to support continuous program improvement, delivery, and quality of administrative support.

1. **Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC**
 - a. Continue to promote processes **that increase a successful application rate among project applicants.**
 - b. Continue to fund projects that represent geographically diverse, underserved and Covid-19 vulnerable communities.
 - i. Of the projects that have reported during this reporting period, Hispanic/Latino, Black/African American, and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations were the most common underserved population served by C2G projects.
 - ii. Some populations to focus on when recruiting future projects include projects that **include Tribal nation target populations and American Indian/Alaska Native and Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander target populations, as well as residents of nursing homes.** These underserved and COVID-19 vulnerable populations are the least represented among current funded projects.
2. **Address challenges cited by projects**
 - a. Projects continue to report challenges related to **outreach, testing hesitancy and testing site.**
 - i. Outreach and testing hesitancy is being addressed via webinars.
 - b. **Testing supply challenges** were also the most cited roadblock that has been resolved by projects. Projects may benefit from learning how others have overcome similar roadblocks.
 - c. Maintaining **continuous feedback loops** between the UNC Evaluation team, the C2G administration team and C2G awardees.

Conclusion. The T&E team aims to measure and assess the C2G program's productivity, and progress made toward program aims and outcomes. The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the C2G program's effectiveness, performance, and community engagement. This is done through 6-month and 12-month surveys, and tracking of program records. The purpose of this interim evaluation report is to cover the evaluation of the RADx-UP Community Collaboration Mini Grant program (C2G) from January 1 through June 30, 2022.

Currently, there are a total of 39 C2G Projects across 4 funding cycles (Cycle 1 n=12 funded Projects; Cycle 2=6 funded Project; Cycle 3 n= 5 projects; and Cycle 4 n = 16 projects). **Over 27,000 tests have been administered across all the 12 projects. COVID-19 training and education, and development and dissemination of COVID-19 testing communication materials** are the most common project activities. At the time of this report, over **90 percent** of projects include an activity to provide training or education to their community around COVID-19 testing projects. **Seventy six percent** of projects are developing and disseminating COVID-19 testing communication materials.

Next steps for evaluation reporting. The T&E team will continue to:

1. Monitor C2G program progress through the 6-month and 12-month surveys, and reports will be completed every six months.
2. Create: (i) individual Project Impact Profiles co-developed with each project to highlight their respective project outcomes, and community and clinical benefits and (ii) an Aggregate C2G Impact Profile to visualize program-level outcomes and TSBM benefits across projects.
3. Additionally, the T&E team will begin to conduct 18-month sustainability interviews in August 2022 with a representative from each C2G project at approximately six months after project close out to learn more about the longer-term project impacts and accomplishment achieved since the conclusion of their grant period.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP C2G Evaluation Logic Model

Appendix 2. RADx-UP C2G TSBM Project Impact Profiles

Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

Translational Science
Benefits Model

IMPACT PROFILE

The Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Program (C2G) has funded **39** projects and **over 27,000** people have been reached through project testing efforts.

Key Benefits: An In-Depth Look

The figure below illustrates the TSBM Indicators¹ and the number of projects by cycle with which their outcomes correspond with.

CLINICAL

Clinical

- **69% of projects** reported a clinical benefit related to their project outcomes
- Example of outcomes include COVID-19 testing procedures...
 - any project that provides COVID tests and results to individuals

COMMUNITY

Community and Public Health

- **All projects (100%)** have at least one outcome that **aligns with community and public health benefits**, since these are mainly community-based interventions focused on a specific community target population.
- Community and public health indicators include community health services, health education resources, healthcare accessibility, testing delivery and uptake, healthcare quality and public health practices
- Examples of outcomes include...
 - The implementation of community-based interventions such as community testing events or mobile testing units
 - Development of COVID-19 educational resources such as flyers or social media posts

ECONOMIC

Economic

- **62% of projects** reported an economic benefit related to their project outcomes.
- Examples of outcomes include...
 - Providing free COVID-19 at home test kits to individuals
 - Potential cost savings on transportation costs by utilizing a mobile testing clinic

¹https://cpb-us-w2.wpmucdn.com/sites.wustl.edu/dist/4/1094/files/2021/08/TSBM_IndicatorswithdDefsandRationales.pdf

The First Central Baptist Church Health Project

The First Central Baptist Church (FCBC) Health project aims to support their community in overcoming barriers to critical COVID-19 information, prevention measures, and diagnostic testing, and promote increased participation in self-isolation measures and contact tracing efforts.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community
Collaboration Mini-Grant
Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The FCBC project resulted in clinical and community and public health benefits.

Through collaboration with other community-based organizations, the FCBC project reduced and removed barriers to COVID-19 testing and diagnosis and improved upon strategies for communication of prevention strategies and test results to underserved and vulnerable populations in North Shore Staten Island, NY.

The Challenge

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic **has severely exacerbated challenges** faced by the Staten Island, New York City community and proved another instance of significant disparity in the accessibility of public health information and services to racial and ethnic minority populations, elderly residents, and low-income families.

The FCBC community has seen a COVID-19 death rate significantly exceeding both the New York City and national death rates^{1, 2}.

The Approach

Through a collaboration between church leadership, community volunteers, culturally competent staff, and community partners, FCBC aims to coordinate and implement programmatic and service-based activities to address the objectives of the RADx Community Collaboration initiative.

The initiative leverages First Central Baptist Church's strong organizational capacity and relationship with the target community to strategically and effectively:

- Conduct Awareness and Education Activities,
- Promote and Coordinate Diagnostic Testing Services,
- Promote Contact Tracing Participation, and
- Engage a Coalition of Community Partners and Stakeholders.

The Team: Central Family Life Center, NYPD, Northwell Community Center, United Way, Choose Healthy Life

Contact: Dennis Samuel, Associate Minister First Central Baptist Church, mdennis@centralfamilylifecenter.org

Find out more: <https://www.centralfamilylifecenter.org/>

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

The FCBC Health project

Served Black/African American populations and Hispanic/Latino populations, senior citizens, and low-income individuals and families in the historically disadvantaged community of North Shore Staten Island, New York City.

Resulted in:

300 people per week reached as part of testing efforts

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

COVID-19 testing services performed for individuals in the community to diagnose and prevent the spread of COVID-19.

COMMUNITY

Increased capacity for COVID-19 testing and vaccination through education and outreach.

COMMUNITY

Promoted accessibility to COVID-19 testing services through innovative outreach methods and collaboration with community organizations.

COMMUNITY

Increased community knowledge of precautions to be taken to avoid COVID-19 infection.

Translational
Science
Benefits Model³

¹NYC Health: COVID-19 Neighborhood Data Profiles; ²John Hopkins University & Medicine Coronavirus Resource Center: Mortality Analyses; ³Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>. Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

La Maestra: COVID-19 Community Outreach & Response for Underserved Populations Project

La Maestra increases COVID-19 education, testing, vaccination, and treatment through outreach to vulnerable communities in San Diego, California.

RADx-UP CDCC
Community
Collaboration Mini-Grant
Program

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The COVID-19 Community Outreach & Response for Underserved Populations project resulted in clinical, community and public health benefits.

Through the creation of an educational campaign, the project provided education and outreach to over 4,000 patients, with materials translated to multiple languages to reflect the multiple populations served. Additionally, the project worked with community-based organizations to provide COVID-19 testing and vaccination services to thousands of individuals in the San Diego area.

The Challenge

La Maestra recognizes the immense impact the 2019 novel coronavirus has had on San Diegans. In San Diego County alone, COVID-19 has directly affected 268,627 individuals that have tested positive for the virus, as of Mar. 25, 2021. Additionally, **unemployment rates** in San Diego County are 8.1% as of January 2021, which is **higher than the national rate** of 6.8% during the same time, leaving thousands of San Diegans struggling to meet basic needs¹.

The Approach

La Maestra's aim is to increase outreach efforts by using the organization's existing mobile unit, strengthening existing partnerships, and providing culturally and linguistically competent education about COVID-19 testing and vaccinations. Key activities include:

- Creation of an educational campaign and outreach to underserved communities to promote the COVID-19 vaccine, COVID-19 testing information
- Mobile unit testing for harder to reach populations that have low testing and vaccination rates
- The collection and analysis of patient data to continue to use best practices in fighting COVID-19

The Team: Corinne Hanson, Chief Development Officer; Noemi Romo, Director of Health Education

Contact: Corinne Hanson, Chief Development Officer, La Maestra Family Clinic, chanson@lamaestra.org

Find out more: <https://lamaestra.org/>

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

La Maestra: COVID-19 Community Outreach & Response project...

Served Black/African American, Hispanic/Latino, Asian American, American Indian/Alaska Native, Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander, socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, underserved rural populations, and sexual and gender minority populations

Resulted in:

6,970 people reached as part of testing efforts

8,893 individuals vaccinated against COVID-19

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

Utilized a mobile testing unit to provide COVID-19 testing and vaccination services to communities.

COMMUNITY

Increased accessibility to COVID-19 testing and vaccination for underserved communities in San Diego, CA.

COMMUNITY

Provided COVID-19 testing and vaccine education and outreach to promote health on an individual and community basis.

ECONOMIC

Potential cost savings benefit through the use of a mobile clinic to reduce transportation costs/time to get tested and vaccinated

Translational
Science
Benefits Model²

¹Department, E. (2021, March 12). California unemployment sits at 9% for January. Retrieved April 01, 2021, from <https://edd.ca.gov/Newsroom/unemployment-january-2021.htm>;

²Institute of Clinical & Translational Sciences at Washington University in St. Louis. Translational Science Benefits Model website. <https://translationalsciencebenefits.wustl.edu>.

Published February 1, 2019. Accessed May 31, 2022.

Appendix 3. RADx-UP C2G 6-month Dashboard Report

6

Projects Reporting

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Partner Organizations

Partner Organizations by Type

Project Organizations by Type

Project Organization Area of Focus

COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Underserved Communities

Project Activities

Challenges

Challenges by Type

CDCC Services

CDCC Impact

